

EUCALYPTUS STORAGE PERFORMANCE AFTER DEBRANCHING

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ABSTRACT: Short and medium rotation coppice (SRC and MRC) have been identified as an interesting solid biomass resource at global level. The production of large amount of biomass in limited time is no longer complicated thanks to modern machine technology, but the concentrated availability of wood fuel often does not go in line with the demand for energy in cases where this demand is high and steady all along the year. This lack of alinement implies the need to find storage solutions to buffer fluctuations in supply and demand. The goal of this study was to understand the storage performance of 5 years old Eucalyptus whole trees, with and without branches, obtained from an MRC plantation located in central Italy (42°10'19''N latitude, 12°62'66''E longitude). Fuel quality parameters were evaluated periodically during a 8 months period from March to September 2018, being the first attempt to store Eucalyptus in this area.

Keywords: Eucalyptus, storage, debranching, fuel quality, dry matter, biomass supply.

1 INTRODUCTION

Short and medium rotation coppice (SRC and MRC) appear to be an interesting strategy for supplying bioenergy plants at global level. The fast-growing capacity and the low agronomic input requirements offer the opportunity to produce high quantities of biomass in low-productive soils, without competing with food crops for fertile arable land [1]. Such crops are recognized to work as mechanism for decentralising energy supplies and promoting the local use of bioenergy [2], contributing also to improve local biodiversity and playing an important role in the sustainable intensification of agriculture [3].

According to production strategy, woody biomass can be obtained exploiting fast-growing hardwood species to be harvested at biennial or quinquennial cycles [4]. Commonly, coppicing is performed when plants are in dormancy, corresponding to the winter season in Northern Hemisphere. This rule shortens the production period from 12 to 5 months, concentrating the availability of biomass in determined periods of the year. Harvesting and producing large amount of biomass in limited time is no longer complicated thanks to modern machine technology [5], however the concentrated availability of wood fuel often does not go in line with the demand for energy, when high and steady all along the year [6]. This lack of alinement implies the need to find storage solutions to buffer fluctuations in supply and demand [7]. In addition, the immediate use of fresh biomass is often unfeasible because the product presents determined quality characteristics that make it non appropriate for certain energy purposes.

Storage can be an opportunity to decrease the moisture content and therefore increase the quality of the product to be efficiently converted [8]. Moreover, storage can be considered one of the rare processes where no costly operations are carried out during the active phase, but where correct preventive measures can improve the quality of the fuel even an increase of the energy content respect to the starting conditions as demonstrated by [9]. Scientists showed that biomass fuel quality is determined in specific cases by the storage process [10] and important fuel quality characteristics such as calorific value,

moisture content and ash content are influenced by storage dynamics [9].

Much of the success of the storage operation is related to the speed rate of drying and the exposure of biomass to biological agents [11]; the latter aspect is related to the storage format (chips, briquettes, logs), which determines the amount of wood that is exposed to air and ground during storage, coming in contact with fungal spores and bacteria. As demonstrated, the moist environment and the exposure of wood to microorganisms are factors influencing the biological processes occurring during storage of woody biomass, which determine dry matter losses and consequently energy losses [11, 12].

This is the reason why scientists suggest in case of forest trees, to store the biomass as whole stem until shortly before the final conversion to preserve the dry matter even though the drying process occur in most cases slower compared to chips [13]. However, storing the whole stem instead of chips is complicated because woody biomass is difficult to handle and require very large spaces generally outdoors, without covering infrastructures. Therefore, when storing whole wood trees long periods are required to obtain acceptable levels of moisture content to have an efficient conversion.

To facilitate the logistic, an alternative method to the storage of whole stem is the comminution. In this case, trees and branches are chipped immediately after felling and transported to the power plant, to be stored in a specific storage site. The chipping of fresh biomass has the advantage of reducing transport cost, facilitate the handling and provide immediate forest cleaning, but it is demonstrated to be less effective than the previous option as high dry matter losses can occur, especially if the biomass remains unused for long periods [6]. However, in some cases, as for SRC, the comminution of fresh biomass is mandatory because the management of numerous small and thin stems would be unpractical and uneconomic. For these type of biomass resources, the market offers specialized machines that perform cutting and chipping in a single pass, streamlining significantly the energy chain [14].

While for large forest trees and SRC a tailor-made storage path can be identified, in the case of MRC there

are still uncertainties that need to be clarified with scientific research. An interesting option for MRC could be the on-field drying, because trees present larger diameters respect the maximum range of workability of SRC technology, but at the same time they have lower bulk density compared to forest stems and do not require prolonged storage period to dry [13]. Limited studies focused on on-field storage of MRC have been identified for the Mediterranean region [13, 15]. These studies display positive results in terms of drying rate and dry matter losses, but the experiences are limited to few storage variables. Among the different species used for MRC, Eucalyptus plantation has acquired interest in Italy, because of its high production and its fast growing. In addition, new tolerant clones were developed in the last years to be exploited in Mediterranean/Temperate climates like those of central Italy [16]. The goal of this study was to understand the storage performance of 5 years old Eucalyptus whole trees, with and without branches, obtained from an MRC plantation located in central Italy. Fuel quality parameters were evaluated periodically during a 8 month period from March to September 2018. It has been the first attempt to store Eucalyptus in this area.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Field characteristics

The research was conducted between February and September 2018 (6 months) at CREA-IT in Monterotondo, near Rome, Central Italy (42°10'19"N latitude, 12°62'66"E longitude) characterized by a Mediterranean climate. The plants used for the study were obtained from an experimental field of five years old Eucalyptus situated at CREA-IT facilities in 2013, four different clones were used (namely the n.7, the n. 358, the n. 14, and the n. 81) to evaluate adaptability and growth rate in climatic conditions typical of Central Italy (preliminary results provided by [16]). The planting layout was 3 x 2 m, with a total plant density of 1600 p/ha. The stand was grown on a flat area of about 1 ha characterized by alluvial soil, with a silty clay soil texture as determined in previous studies [17].

2.2 Experimental layout

The storage trial took place outdoors using 60 Eucalyptus plants fell down using a chainsaw and hauled at the field edge with a tractor fork. Half of the plants were debranched (Stem Storage) and piled in 2 heaps of 15 plants each. The remaining 30 plants were left with branches and leaves (Whole tree Storage) to form two other piles. Each pile was formed by 5 layers of plants, starting from 5 plants at ground level till one plant in the top. Therefore, the experimental layout was composed by 4 piles of whole trees of 15 plants each, 2 with and 2 without branches, none of them covered and all of them exposed to same climatic conditions. Climatic parameters such as precipitation, wind speed and average air temperature were recorded during the entire test. Data were recorded using a weather cab "Davis vantage pro 2" placed approximately 200 m from the storage site.

Figure 1: Wood pile for stem storage (up) and whole tree storage (down).

2.3 Fuel characterization

At time of harvesting, 5 samples of wood stem were selected as according to the methodology proposed by [18] to analyse initial moisture content of the material according to the international standard [19]. Each pile of trees was weighed using a dynamometer of PCE Italia Srl (CS 1000N model - range of measurement 1000 kg and sensitivity 0.2 kg), at felling date, every 30 days and at the end of the storage period (15th of October) in order to calculate the mass variation due to losses of dry mass and to moisture content reduction. In this regard, concurrently with the day of weighing, 10 samples of wood stem for each pile were randomly selected to determine the moisture content, following the methodology above referenced. Only wood stem was considered in this study in order to evaluate the effect of the leaves on wood drying by comparing moisture content variation of plant with or without branches.

2.4 Statistically analysis

After verifying the normality of the distributions, the data statistically significant were analysed by ANOVA [20]. The Tukey test ($P < 0.05$) was used as post-hoc test to separate the means.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

During the storage period the total rainfall recorded was 665.8 mm. The mean temperature during the whole storage period was 17.97 °C, and the mean monthly rainfall was 73.98 mm. Maximum and minimum temperature were registered respectively in July (38.4 °C) and February (-8.7 °C), while the maximum amount of precipitation was recorded in March (179.4 mm) and the minimum in September (13.2 mm). The evolution of weather values is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Weather data of the storage period.

At time of harvest, after five years of cultivation, the mean height of the plants was 9.7 m and the mean diameter was 13.08 cm. The total weight of the plant was 68.17 kg on average, representing the stem the 56 % of the total plant. The moisture content was 50.56 % (w%-ar). In table 1 the mean results of storage performances on the stem are depicted.

Table I: Mean values of storage performances

Storage type	Initial stem moisture content (w%-ar)	Final stem moisture content (w%-ar)	Dry matter losses in stem (%)
Stem Storage (SS)	50.56	15.01 a	4.26 a
Whole tree Storage (WS)		12.17 b	17.75 b

The storage process caused a reduction of 28.3 % of moisture content and 4.26 % of dry matter in the case of the stem. The whole tree storage instead experienced a reduction of moisture content of 88.9 % and of dry matter of 17.75 %.

The differences between the two treatments in terms of final moisture content and losses of dry matter were statistically significant ($P < 0.05$).

The moisture content reduction achieved in both treatments during the 6 months have reached interesting figures for thermochemical processes. The larger reduction of moisture content of the WS with respect to the SS can be explained by the presence of leaves, which foster the evaporation of water from the vegetal structure [21].

The rainfall recorded in October, 52.2 mm, caused an increase of moisture content of 4.33 % in the SS piles, while a 1.3 % in the WS piles. Reducing the storage time until the end of September would have avoided the autumnal precipitation, producing a biomass with lower value of moisture content.

Regarding dry-matter losses, the results achieved by SS are in line with those obtained in other studies such as in the storage experience of whole young trees of downy birch performed in Sweden by [22]. On the other hand, the high losses identified in WS piles should be ascribed to the drying and falling process of the leaves, as also the initial

amount of leave-biomass of eucalyptus trees was very high (about 44% of tree branches and leaves). However, the amount of leaves lost was not quantified and this consideration should be validated scientifically.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The results of this study demonstrate that eucalyptus tree with branches and leaves during storage have behaved in a different way respect stored eucalyptus trunks, even if the initial moisture content was the same in both WS and SS. This means that the storage form had a strong effect on the quality of the biomass/storage performance.

Wood debranching has reduced the drying speed rate of trunks that in the case of WS was favoured by the presence of leaves. Indeed, storing the Eucalyptus biomass as whole tree could be a possible solution to increase and speed up the drying process. At the end of the storage it would be still possible to comminute the dry biomass to produce chip, or to debranch the plants to use as logs or firewood. Further studies would be needed to verify the quality of the biomass obtained from whole eucalyptus trees, with trunks and leaves, to evaluate the final potential energy uses.

5 REFERENCES

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